

Sobre una generalización de la función hipergeométrica de Gauss

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Dedicated to Professor Shyam Kalla

On the occasion of his 76th birthday

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Resumen

El trabajo trata una nueva generación de la función hipergeométrica de Gauss, ${}_rF^{\tau,\beta}(a,b;c;z)$. Se demuestran las propiedades básicas de esta función (representación en serie, formulas diferenciales, relaciones fraccionales, representación integral, relación de tipo Erdelyi).

Palabras y frases claves: r -función hipergeométrica, función gamma (τ,β) , – función hipergeométrica confluyente.

On one generalization of the Gauss’ hypergeometric function

Abstract

The paper devoted to the new generalization of the hypergeometric Gauss’ function, ${}_rF^{\tau,\beta}(a,b;c;z)$. The basic properties of this function (the representation by series, the differential formulas, the fractional relations, integral representations, the relation of type Erdelyi) are proved.

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Key words and phrases: r - hypergeometric function, gamma-function, (τ,β) , – confluent hypergeometric function .

Introduction

Further studying of the special functions is prospective and very useful for the different branches of science.

The continuous development of the mechanics of solid medium, mathematical physics, probability theory, aerodynamics, astronomy and others has led to the generalization and creation of new classes of special functions [1], [2], [3].

In this article we consider the r – generalized Gauss’ hypergeometric function, its properties.